

Rhenium. Part II.* Polarographic Study of $[\text{ReO}_2\text{py}_4]\text{Cl}$

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The polarographic reduction of $[\text{ReO}_2\text{py}_4]^+$ in KCl was studied using a dropping mercury cathode. The polarogram showed a single cathodic reduction wave at a half wave potential of -1.00 volt vs. S.C.E. at 28° . The reduction was reversible involving one electron. By measuring the half wave potentials as a function of different concentrations of free pyridine added, it was shown that in the reduced state the complex species contains two pyridine molecules.

In a previous communication¹ it was observed that the pentavalent rhenium complex with pyridine, viz., $[\text{ReO}_2\text{py}_4]\text{Cl}$ results when chloro complexes of rhenium are boiled with aqueous pyridine, irrespective of the oxidation state of rhenium in the parent chloro complexes. This fact reflects on the greater stability of pyridine complexes of Re(V) compared to those of Re(II), Re(III), and Re(IV), if they exist at all. The only pyridine complexes of Re(IV) are $\text{pyH}[\text{RepyCl}_5]$ and $[\text{Repy}_2\text{Cl}_4]$ which were obtained by Babeshkina and Tronev² and $[\text{Repy}_2\text{I}_4]$ prepared by Colton, Levitus and Wilkinson³. Only one complex of Re(III) with pyridine, Repy_2Cl_3 , has been reported. No complexes of Re(II) with pyridine have yet been prepared. In view of this, it is interesting to study the behaviour of $[\text{ReO}_2\text{py}_4]\text{Cl}$ towards reducing agents.

Attempts were made to reduce $[\text{ReO}_2\text{py}_4]\text{Cl}$ with a number of reducing agents with a view to isolate lower valent compounds. The reducing agents employed were sodium amalgam, zinc, sodium hypophosphite, hypophosphorous acid, hydroxylamine hydrochloride and stannous chloride. In no case any positive inference could be drawn regarding the formation of lower valent complexes.

Thus being unsuccessful in drawing any evidence of the formation of lower valent rhenium complexes with pyridine by reducing Re(IV) complex with chemical agents, the electro-chemical reduction of $[\text{ReO}_2\text{py}_4]\text{Cl}$ has been studied polarographically.

The polarogram of $[\text{ReO}_2\text{py}_4]\text{Cl}$ in $0.2 M$ KCl showed a single cathodic reduction wave at a half wave potential of -1.00 volt vs. S.C.E. at 28° (Fig. 1). A second wave arising beyond -1.3 volt vs. S.C.E. was due to the catalytic wave of hydrogen which is observed with many rhenium compounds⁵. The plot of $\log \frac{i_d - i}{i}$ vs. $E_{d.e}$ (Fig. 2) gave a straight

* A preliminary note on the work was published in *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1963, **40**, 1045.

1. M. C. Chakravorti, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1970, **47**, No. 9, Part I, of this series.
2. G. K. Babeshkina and V. G. Tronev, *Zhur. Neorg. Khim.*, 1958, **3**, 2458; *Dokl. Akad. Nauk SSSR*, 1963, **152**(1), 100.
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line indicating that the reduction was reversible. The slope of the straight line was 0.065 showing that the reduction involved one electron, the calculated value of the slope for $n = 1$ being 0.060 at 28°. Thus, under the experimental conditions Re(V) in $[\text{ReO}_2\text{py}_4]^+$ is reduced to Re(IV) .

Fig. 2. Polarogram of $[\text{ReO}_2\text{py}_4]\text{Cl}$ in presence of pyridine

For determining the composition of the complex in the reduced state the half wave potentials of the electrolyte were measured as a function of the concentration of free pyridine which was progressively added to it. The half wave potentials were a linear function of the logarithm of the concentration of the corresponding pyridine added. Applying the equation⁶,

$$E_{\frac{1}{2}} = E^{\circ} + \frac{0.060}{n} \log \frac{K_{ox}}{K_{red}} - \frac{0.060}{n} (p-q) \log C$$

Fig. 3. Logarithmic plot

$(p-q)$ was calculated from the slope of the linear plot of $E_{\frac{1}{2}}$ vs. $\log C$ (Fig. 3) where C is the concentration of free pyridine. The value of n was put to be unity. The slope was found to be equal to 0.107 and thus $(p-q)$ came out to be 1.81. Since p , the number of pyridine

6. I. M. Kolthoff and J. J. Lingane, "Polarography", Interscience Publishers, Inc., New York, N.Y., 1946, p. 172.

molecules in the complex of Re(V) is equal to 4, the value of q , the number of pyridine molecules in the complex of Re(IV) when rounded up becomes equal to 2.

Fig. 3. $E_{1/2}$ vs concentration of pyridine added.

EXPERIMENTAL

$1.70 \times 10^{-3} M$ solution of $[\text{ReO}_2\text{py}_4]\text{Cl}$ was prepared by dissolving a known amount of the recrystallised air-dried sample of $[\text{ReO}_2\text{py}_4]\text{Cl} \cdot 2\text{H}_2\text{O}$ in a known volume of $0.2 M$ KCl solution.

The polarogram was recorded in a Cambridge pen-recording polarograph. The cell used was of conventional H shape with a built-in-saturated calomel half cell separated by a sintered glass partition. The conventional dropping mercury cathode arrangement was used. Electrolytic hydrogen was used to make the solution free from oxygen. The drop time of the cathode was 3.08 sec. at an applied potential of -0.50 volt vs. S.C.E. and 2.29 sec. at an applied potential of -1.60 volt. 'm' was 1.7 mg. per second.

A typical polarogram is shown in Fig. 1. $E_{1/2}$ was computed from the polarogram itself and also from the usual log plot (Fig. 2).

A dilute solution of pyridine was prepared by diluting redistilled pyridine with double distilled water. The solution was made $0.2 M$ with respect to KCl. The pyridine concentration was determined by titrating with a standard hydrochloric acid using bromophenol blue as indicator. The strength was found to be $4.65 \times 10^{-2} M$. 5.0 ml. of $[\text{ReO}_2\text{py}_4]\text{Cl}$ was taken in the cell and hydrogen passing through a bubbler containing the same electrolyte of identical concentrations, was passed through it. The polarogram was then recorded. From a microburette the standard solution of pyridine was progressively added in identical volumes to both the electrolyte and the bubbler. Each time before recording the polarogram hydrogen was passed through the electrolyte. The polarograms recorded against different volumes of pyridine are shown in Fig. 1. The concentration of free pyridine was not varied beyond about $4 \times 10^{-3} M$, since as its concentration was gradually increased, the reduction wave was found to be gradually shifted towards more negative potentials and ultimately overlapping with the catalytic hydrogen wave, thus making the computation of half wave potentials difficult, and also because the pH of the solution would then vary appreciably.

In passing from the minimum ($0.916 \times 10^{-3} M$) to the maximum ($4.245 \times 10^{-3} M$) concentration of added pyridine the $p\text{H}$ of the medium was increased by only about 0.3 units. It can thus be assumed that the variation of E_1 with the addition of pyridine was solely due to the variation in the concentration of ligand pyridine. No attempt was made to record the polarograms of $[\text{ReO}_2\text{py}_4]\text{Cl}$ in buffered medium of alkaline range $p\text{H}$, since the complex decomposes in alkaline solutions with the liberation of pyridine¹.

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